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Cybersecurity on 5G Technology

Introduction

The 5G technology brings big concerns to the cybersecurity as will be more easy to use malware and tools to hacker system for spying, data stealing and malware attacks. China is the leader of this technology and is prepared to interfere with the sovereignty of other countries through communications systems.

Ensuring the integrity, reliability and robustness of industrial, smart cities, administration and national defence communication is a mandatory requirement. At the same time, important architecture and design specifications for 5G are currently being defined. Security cannot be implemented later. It must be integrated into the design from the very beginning in order to achieve the above-mentioned goals and thus the industrial suitability. The companies want customization of the standard in their industrial applications - especially for security mechanisms. Only by incorporating security into standardization as early as possible can this flexibility and the added value for users be realized.

In a simple way 5G will be explained for a better understanding and discussion of this important issue of cybersecurity.

Artur Victoria

5G

More innovation, more prosperity, and more social security: 5G is the key to the digital world.

Digitization opens a new chapter in the history of technological, economic and social change. Already so far, new technologies have given us completely new scope for action: they have made life easier and better for people. They have changed and developed worldviews. They have helped make broad prosperity and social security possible through innovation and economic dynamism.

From vision to reality

Digitization promises significant development impulses in many areas of everyday life and the economy:

- Automated mobility reduces congestion, emissions and traffic accidents.
- Digital factories not only make production easier, faster and more reliable - the location becomes secondary.

- Digitization will enable a "smart", climate-friendly energy system in which one can be both a consumer and a producer of green energy.

- The healthcare system is getting better and more efficient through digital solutions. New diagnostic options or medical monitoring in your own home promote life expectancy and quality of life.

- In education, digitization allows for time and place independent learning - the potentials of lifelong learning become reality.

- Digitization will improve many public administration processes to allow citizens easier access to public services.

Full computerization in the manufacturing sector (Industry 4.0), the widespread use of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) or the penetration of our world with "Internet of Things" applications are often still visions and future scenarios. Many ideas and concepts are waiting to be finally put into action.

The digitization of a country has a significant impact on economic and social prosperity.

5G strategy

5G is the infrastructural "key" for the new digital worlds: A powerful IT infrastructure that makes ubiquitous computing and the transmission of large amounts of data possible. Together with the broadband infrastructure, this requires an extremely high-performance mobile network: In addition to mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets, enormous amounts of data will be exchanged between vehicles, household appliances or industrial plants. This networking places completely new demands on the capacity, security and quality of the radio-based mobile connection.

The 5G standard is the gateway to the digital world of the future. It is the key to Industry, autonomous mobility, smart cities and smart villages, comprehensive cybersecurity, cutting-edge education or the Internet of Things. This is also illustrated by the technological comparison: Compared to today's standards, 5G should have a capacity that is 1,000 times higher, a connection density of at least 100 times, peak data rates of up to 10 Gbit / s and a factor of 10 increased energy efficiency. This underscores the disruptive nature of a tightly knit digital high-performance network as a breakthrough technology.

Make digitization active

Support for research and development, especially in the areas of Big Data, Artificial Intelligence and the Internet of Things, provides important impetus for innovation in mobility, production, agriculture, logistics, services, energy, healthcare, education and

the media industry. The 5G of digitalization can be expected in these areas enormous growth potential.

5G strategy sees itself as a responsible instrument for shaping digital change and its opportunities. Digitization is not a matter of course. In order to be able to use positive effects and master the challenges of digital transformation, a future-oriented design of the framework conditions of digital transformation is indispensable.

5G has the potential to accelerate processes as a disruptive factor in digitization.

Good general conditions are the basis for the development of innovative services and applications.

The European Union has defined the importance of 5G high performance networks as an important tool for Europe to compete on the world market. The Action Plan "5G for Europe" identifies improved coordination between national approaches in the context of the introduction of 5G networks, the promotion of investment in 5G networks and the implementation of standards as concrete objectives.

Austria has a good starting position and is above the European average in terms of digitization as well as the stationary and mobile availability of digital infrastructures. Digital administration is also very well developed in Austria. Austria has a backlog compared to other states, especially with regard to the availability of fiber optic networks.

Overview of global 5G development

China

Several years ago, China set up a "5G Promotion Group", where telecommunications companies, ICT companies, universities and research institutes are working together to develop 5G.

China wants to play a pioneering role at 5G, both technologically and in terms of network expansion (planned nationwide rollout of 5G by 2020) and is also actively involved in standardization.

South Korea

As one of the pioneers for 5G, South Korea has already commissioned a 5G test network at the 2018 Winter Olympics in Pyeongchang. Since 2013, there have been 5G initiatives and several successful 5G field trials. Also in South Korea, a commercial start of 5G is expected for 2020.

Japan

A 5G test network went live in the Tokyo area in 2017 with the goal of testing the performance of 5G in live operation. Japan plans to have a nationwide 5G network in operation by the time of the 2020 Summer Olympics.

USA

The four major US telecommunications companies are actively collaborating with ICT companies on 5G standardization. The government also launched a research initiative a year ago and the regulator FCC already offers test frequencies for 5G. Also in the US, a commercial launch of 5G is expected in 2020.

Sweden

In Europe, Sweden is one of the 5G pioneers, there are already several successful field trials and in 2018 Stockholm, as the first capital in Europe, will receive a 5G test network.

Germany

In 2016, the German federal government adopted a 5G strategy and set up a Dialogue Forum 5G to network research, telecommunications companies and industry partners. Germany wants to assume global leadership in 5G applications in particular and has already successfully rolled out test fields for autonomous driving on the motorways (eg on the A8 near Munich).

In Germany, the world's first 5G test center was also opened by Vodafone Germany at the end of August 2017 in cooperation with the University of Aachen in Aldenhoven. In addition, after a nationwide beauty contest by the industry association BITKOM, the first real digital city in Darmstadt will be set up.

Fields of action for concrete measures

In particular, the 5G rollout will depend on preconditions such as existing and available infrastructure, a positive investment and innovation climate and, of course, demand for services and applications. The following requirements are a priority for successful goal achievement:

- a. Investment-friendly climate for new technologies
- b. Nationwide available and accessible fiber infrastructure
- c. Significant amount of new frequency spectrum
- d. Demand for digital technologies and applications

e. New digital value chains and business models f. 5G-compatible network components and devices

Essentially, the fields of action are divided into two segments in which specific measures were developed:

Infrastructure and Applications

Infrastructure

The digital infrastructure as the connecting basis is the nervous system of the digital society and indispensable for a high-performance and functional business location. The development and dissemination of digital applications, products and services in society and business requires a high-performance, nationwide broadband infrastructure.

The creation of the infrastructural conditions for a sustainable broadband supply and the rollout of a 5G network represent an enormous challenge and opportunity for all concerned.

Thanks to an investment-friendly climate, investments in the grids can be stimulated on the one hand, and the chances of 5G technology for developers and users to establish internationally successful services and applications at an early stage, on the other hand.

As part of the stakeholder survey, several fields of action were identified that are considered particularly important for the infrastructural expansion of 5G networks.

The central goal is to advance the 5G rollout in a timely manner and as widely as possible by advancing the 5G readiness, so that Austria can assume a pioneering role in international comparison.

As this requires significant investment, this goal can only be achieved if the costs of expansion are significantly reduced and administrative processes are accelerated.

After frequencies represent one of the scarce goods for the 5G rollout and high bandwidths only by a significant increase in the usable frequency spectrum.

To provide frequency bands for normal operation and to determine their procurement modalities. In particular, efforts should be made to ensure long-term planning security for the stakeholders, to actually use the allocated frequencies, and to support any requirements of the broadband strategy, particularly with regard to coverage.

With regard to the densification of the base stations' locations required by the use of frequencies in higher frequency ranges (which allow shorter ranges) and the objective of the participation of all people in Austria in digitization, a significant increase in the number of new locations required is to be expected. These will be so-called small cells,

which are significantly smaller than previous mobile radio antennas. These locations are predominantly connected by fiber optic and will be located closer to the end customers in densely populated areas. For example, facilitation in the construction of transmitters in financial, procedural and organizational terms should accelerate the 5G rollout in order to boost investment in Austria.

In particular, to ensure the widest coverage possible with 5G, the continuation and further development of the support system is required, so that more incentives for investment in optic fiber expansion are created - even in the less densely populated regions and / or the regions with a lower traffic volume.

Optimal framework conditions for digitization as a whole can further support the realization of the introduction of 5G. Just as digitization as a cross-sectional matter and especially 5G as a disruptive technology will permeate all areas of life, so too will the impact of legal measures on digitization and thus also on broadband and 5G in all areas of life have to be considered.

In particular, it should also be considered in the management of frequency resources that there is less need for individual radio frequency resources by shifting communication applications to 5G platforms for other applications.

Frequencies

Timely allocation of frequencies in line with European requirements Due to the foreseeable, exponentially increasing increase in mobile data consumption as a result of increasing transmission capacities in the 5G networks, data transmission in the last mile, i.e. in the access area, urgently requires additional frequencies. These should be made available to the market in a timely manner, with an orientation towards the pioneers in Europe in terms of time.

The awarding of frequencies in the 700 MHz, 1500 MHz, 2100 MHz and 3.4-3.8 GHz bands is scheduled to take place this year and next. In addition, other international frequency bands for 5G

As soon as there is clarity about the availability of such additional tapes, an updated version of the Spectrum Release Plan should be prepared. When determining the rules for determining the highest bids, the regulatory authority must take into account appropriate transparency and predictability, taking into account the award objectives and the legal requirements.

In order to further increase the predictability of the participants in the entire procedure of the award procedure, the concrete rules for determining the highest bids should already be included in the tender document.

Infrastructure Sharing & Frequency Pooling

The deployment of 5G mobile networks raises the issue of sharing infrastructure elements to reduce the cost of upgrading. Flexibility in this area, however, is always in conflict with competition considerations, as intensive cooperation can lead to a reduction in competition (through adjustments in services, pricing and coverage areas).

Due to the further development of the market conditions and the challenges associated with the development of 5G networks, an evaluation of the position at that time, taking into account the objectives of nationwide broadband coverage, up to the tendering of frequencies in the area 3.4 -3.8 GHz. The aim is to facilitate the sharing of infrastructure elements.

Frequency allocations are also subject to regular conditions regarding the use of the allocated frequencies. These must be proportionate, transparent and non-discriminatory.

The public-service requirements should therefore be shaped according to the technical and economic conditions in line with the general policy objectives relating to the development of high-speed networks.

5G Applications

Transport: cooperative, connected and automated mobility

In an ideal future, there will be no more congestion on the roads, no accidents and little more emissions, as the vehicles will operate autonomously, communicate with each other and be moved with new drives.

This may be a long-term vision for the future, but it is clear that in the coming years, there is considerable potential in terms of mobility for new technology improvements. The increasing real-time connectivity of people and goods provides an important basis for transport connectivity and for virtually all new, sustainable mobility services. In particular, 5G will enable new real-time data communication between multiple vehicles and between vehicle and infrastructure.

5G has the potential, together with other established communication technologies (ITS-G5, etc.), to become part of a future "Digital Transport Infrastructure" that guarantees real-time services to citizens and makes a significant contribution to making traffic safer, more efficient and more environmentally friendly shape. In order to guarantee robust, reliable and safety-critical services in the area of mobility, a successful coexistence of various communication technologies must be ensured. Thus,

with the introduction of 5G and the development of appropriate application technologies, attention must be paid to successful networking and integration into the existing digital infrastructure.

In a first phase, safe, networked and automated services and applications for rail and road will be tested under real conditions. Pilot projects should pay attention to the development of marketable implementations, new business models and applications, transport policy potential, and adding value and competitiveness to the participating industrial partners. Automated driving is an important aspect in the context of the continuous change in our mobility, which will play a key role in the development of the transport system of the future.

Industry - factory of the future

Tomorrow's factory is no longer primarily located in locations with favourable wage levels, as automation of production, proximity to sales markets and excellent infrastructure play a much more important role than traditional location factors.

The development of new industrial applications under the keyword "Industry 4.0" has been a topic in many companies for quite some time. The focus here is primarily on automation in the production area, which is linked and optimized with modern information and communication technology.

The technical basis for this is intelligent and digitally networked systems, which make a largely self-organized production possible: people, machines and products communicate and cooperate directly with one another in Industry 4.0.

This networking enables the optimization of entire value chains. All phases of a product life cycle are addressed - from the product idea through research and development, production and use to maintenance and recycling.

Accordingly, the factory of the future is building on automated production, networked machines, time-critical process control and real-time data transfer.

With 5G, all production-relevant factors (employees, machines, workpieces, systems, suppliers, customers, products and logistics) will not only be included in the production process more easily, faster and more reliably, they will also be fail-safe and real-time via intelligent networks communicate with each other, even over long distances.

The efficient interaction of wired and wireless data transmission ensures valuable flexibility. With 5G, this opens up new possibilities for product, process and service design, which have to be researched and, in a further step, tested in corresponding pilot factories.

Energy

5G enables consumers, producers and network operators to be networked in intelligent decentralized energy systems that communicate with one another in real time and can thus be combined in the future into virtual power plants. The smart grids of the future will meet the desire for greater integration of renewable energy sources and the desired increase in efficiency and energy independence. In addition, smart grids can support the introduction and application of new technological developments such as electric vehicles and charging stations or "smart home" applications.

An essential element of future decentralized energy systems will be data-based and technology-supported services - both in the B2B area between players in infrastructure and trade, and at the interface with end consumers.

These services are characterized on the one hand by a high number of participants - and thus many to be networked terminals - on the other hand can be expected with a high degree of dynamics.

The possibility of using millions of networked devices at data transmission rates of up to 10 Gbit / s and high energy efficiency simultaneously with the new mobile radio standard offers great potential for new applications in the energy sector. At the same time the

Intelligent networks are establishing themselves in production processes.

Efficient energy management is based on large, networked data volumes.

Reliability of the future energy infrastructure massively depend on the reliability of the deployed communication infrastructures (and vice versa). This interdependence results in the necessity of designing a resilient overall system of communication and energy, as well as the development of new application technologies in the energy sector.

E-Health

Telemedicine will revolutionize the relationship between doctor and patient and could not only provide better medical care in rural areas, but also the live integration of specialists in other clinics or the live transmission of patient data from ambulances into the clinic and thus generally a more efficient emergency medicine.

Digitization has already reached the health sector and thus medicine in all its fields of application. Purposefully used, it can ensure that patients benefit from better

diagnoses and more individualized treatments, targeted support for older people in their everyday lives, and a generally more efficient healthcare system.

Offers in education and further education as well as in studies pave the way for future professional success. Youth and adult education, the presentation of new job descriptions and definitions, the creation of a platform for the implementation of an in-service training, further education or retraining concept are among the key challenges in this area.

New healthcare services need reliable infrastructure, even in rural areas.

Augmented and Virtual Reality determines the learning environment of tomorrow.

Smart cities

When tendering for research questions on application fields of the new mobile radio standard, the users must be involved. In addition, issues such as acceptance and system integration need to be addressed. The Smart Cities theme is particularly well suited to the development and testing of new digital technologies, as 5G's impact on the urban mobility, environment, energy, ICT and security sectors, and system integration across the different domains, is broadly addressed. Fields of application, can be explored. Therefore, the involvement of relevant stakeholders in research and development activities on smart cities should take into account the effects of new 5G applications in the future.

Administration

Digitization helps to further develop the administration processes in a user-friendly way. The aim must also be to make the most important official channels available to citizens and companies in digital form. Thus, each and every individual has the added value of being able to choose for himself whether an official path is carried out digitally or analogously. This leads either to a no-stop shop or a one-stop shop at the administrative level. 5G enables new applications in dialogue with the administration. For example, it will be possible to conduct video-based communication that will massively increase the quality of life of the population.

Data is provided once by the population and the companies. It must be avoided that many requests from different authorities for a comparable data set lead to an extra effort for individuals or companies. Digitization and the associated new applications ensure that the administration can access the data according to the rights of the requesting institution.

Steps to 5G applications

In order to be able to develop timely and efficient various applications / applications, the 5G strategy sets out concrete steps to enable to play a pioneering role in the development of applications:

Promote Networking - Establishment of a 5G Platform

5G offers a wealth of opportunities for new services, business models, products, applications or savings potential across multiple industry boundaries as the foundation for a modern digital infrastructure. To accelerate active exchange and networking, a 5G platform will be established. Through institutionalized networking, the 5G platform offers space to market participants, researchers and early adopters

Smart cities are suitable for the development and testing of new technologies. 5G optimizes the dialogue with the administration.

Security

Why is dealing with security at 5G already important? Without consideration of security, there will be no use of 5G in the industry. Because ensuring the integrity, reliability and robustness of industrial communication is a mandatory requirement. At the same time, important architecture and design specifications for 5G are currently being defined. Security cannot be implemented later. It must be integrated into the design from the very beginning in order to achieve the above-mentioned goals and thus the industrial suitability. The companies want customization of the standard in their industrial applications - especially for security mechanisms. Only by incorporating security into standardization as early as possible can this flexibility and the added value for users be realized.

- 1) Participant Management Concerns: Alternatives to the SIM card model, no vendor lock-in background: For 5G, flexible management of the individual participants is important. In particular, it should offer alternatives to SIM cards, for example via a certificate-based model. This includes the ability to add, remove and divide devices into groups with different access rights and security requirements, regardless of the Mobile Network Operator (MNO). The management of a large number of devices and groups should be done so that no excessive dependencies on a particular provider arise and continue a healthy competition from different providers is possible. 2) User-specific security layers Concerns: User-specific security mechanisms must also be flexible for higher layers Background: The 5G design should already include

robust security functionalities. Due to the different use cases and customer requirements, however, it should always be possible for the users to implement individual security mechanisms both at the wireless level and at higher levels. In particular, there should be no obstacles to the implementation of proprietary, custom security layers that overlay the 5G layer.

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